

Dyslexia, Dysorthographia and Visual Processing Disorder: Their Para-Symptomatological Differences

Noel Kok Hwee CHIA EdD, FCP, FCoT, FCollP
Board-Certified Educational Therapist
Honorary Advisor
Reading Specialists' Association
Singapore

ABSTRACT

Among the thirteen specific learning disabilities listed under the Level I category LD in The Educator's Diagnostic Manual (EDM) of Disabilities and Disorders (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007), three of them share some para-symptomatological traits (though with different etiologies) that often cause confusion among professionals assessing and/or treating such conditions. They are dyslexia (EDM Level II LD 4.00), dysorthographia (EDM Level II LD 5.00) and visual processing disorder (EDM Level II LD 12.00). In this paper, the author has attempted to use their operating definitions to distinguish the symptomatological differences among the three disabilities/disorders. In addition, using the EDM multilevel coding system, the author has also touched on briefly how it can be used in assessing and/or screening the three specific learning disabilities in order to come to a clear decision on the diagnosis for each of the three disabilities as well as the three tier levels of Response to Intervention (RtI) Initiative.

Key words: *dyslexia, dysorthographia, EDM, symptoms, visual processing disorder*

INTRODUCTION

Under the Individuals with Disabilities Education Improvement Act of 2004 (IDEIA 2004), there are thirteen disability categories: autism, deaf-blindness, developmental delay, emotional disturbance, hearing impairment (including deafness), mental retardation, multiple disabilities, orthopedic impairments, other health impairments, specific learning disabilities, speech or language impairments, traumatic brain injury, and visual impairment (including blindness). Among them, according to the US Department of Education (2004), the highest percentage of students age six to twenty-one, who received special education services under the federal government funding, consists of those with specific language disabilities (47.2% or 2,816,361) (see Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007, pp. xxvi-xxvii).

The IDEIA 2004 has defined specific learning disability as “a disorder in one or more of the basic psychological processes involved in understanding or in using language, spoken or written, that may manifest itself in an imperfect ability to listen, think, speak, read, write, spell, or do mathematical calculations, including conditions such as perceptual disabilities, brain injury, minimal brain dysfunction, dyslexia and developmental aphasia. However, the term does not include learning problems that are primarily the result of visual, hearing or motor disabilities, of mental retardation, of emotional disturbance, or of environmental, cultural, or economic

disadvantage” [34 CFR 300.7(c)(10)]. This definition remains unchanged from the former Individuals with Disabilities Education Act of 1997 (IDEA 1997).

In other words, the key or core symptoms of specific learning disabilities are (1) deficits in one or more psychological processes with (2) perceptual, neurological and developmental challenges, and not the result of (3) sensory-motor disabilities, cognitive retardation, affective disturbance and/or sociocultural-economic disadvantage.

Under the IDEIA 2004 definition, schools do not need to consider if “a child has a severe discrepancy between achievement and intellectual ability in oral expression, listening comprehension, written expression, basic reading skill, reading comprehension, mathematical calculation or mathematical reasoning [USC sec. 614(b)(2)(3)]. To diagnose or assess a child with specific learning disability, a school may use a process to determine if the child respond to scientific, research-based intervention as part of the evaluation procedure. This is normally done by an approved Access Arrangement assessor, who must possess a relevant post-graduate qualification and professional credentials and has been following up with the child for past three years with proper recording done.

Narrowing down to the Level I LD category under the Educator’s Diagnostic Manual of Disabilities and Disorders (EDM) (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007), Level II thirteen specific learning disabilities have been listed as follow in this first category in the EDM: Level II LD 1.00 auditory processing disorders with thirteen specific types of the disorder under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 1.01-1.13); Level II LD 2.00 dyscalculia with thirteen specific types of the disorder under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 2.01-2.13); Level II LD 3.00 dysgraphia with four specific types of the disorder under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 3.01-3.04); Level II LD 4.00 dyslexia with ten specific types of the disorder under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 4.01-4.10); Level II LD 5.00 dysorthographia; Level II LD 6.00 Gerstmann Syndrome; Level II LD 7.00 gifted with learning disabilities (or twice exceptionalities); Level II LD 8.00 non-verbal learning disabilities with four specific disorders under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 8.01-8.04); Level II LD 9.00 organizational learning disorders with six specific types of the disorder under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 9.01-9.06); Level II LD 10.00 sensory integration disorders with five specific types of the disorder under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 10.01-10.05); Level II LD 11.00 social cue disorder; Level II LD 12.00 visual processing disorders with twelve specific types of the disorder under this classification (EDM Level III, LD 12.01-12.12); and Level II LD 13.00 other types of specific learning disabilities, either of idiopathic origin or yet to be discovered.

When one starts to delve deeper into the thirteen disabilities or disorders in this Level II LD category, most cannot help but to notice similar traits being stated over and over again shared among the different specific learning disabilities. Among these specific learning disabilities, three of them seem to be very closely related with overlapping symptoms that may cause difficulties and even confusion to professionals who assess, diagnose and/or treat individuals with such challenging: Level II LD 4.00 dyslexia, Level II LD 5.00 dysorthographia, and Level II LD 12.00 visual processing disorders. We shall examine each of the three specific learning disabilities in the following sections.

DYSLEXIA, DYSORTHOGRAPHIA AND VISUAL PROCESSING DISORDERS

In this section, we shall briefly examine the operating definition of each of the three specific learning disabilities – dyslexia (also known as specific reading disability or just reading disability or disorder), dysorthographia (also known as spelling disability or disorder) and visual processing disorders – and the breaking it down to their respective classification of core symptoms.

Dyslexia (EDM Level I LD, Level II LD 4.00)

Dyslexia has a long history that can be traced back to 1676 when a physician, Dr John Shmidt (cited in Elliott & Grigorenko, 2014) recorded the case of the loss of reading ability that he described it as word blindness (or aphasia). A hundred and eighty-five years later, Broca (1861) concluded in his study that the left anterior area of the brain was critical region for language production. Thirteen years later, Wernicke (1874) described lesions in the posterior portion of the left temporal lobe of the brain led t great difficult in comprehending speech. Today in the field of neuroscience, technologies such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has been used to study the dyslexic brains to confirm that indeed dyslexic brains differ from non-dyslexic ones. Using the focal MRI (fMRI), B. Shaywitz (1995) and S. Shaywitz (1999) have confirmed that the phonological process that takes place during reading and/or spelling involves an area in the left hemispheric region of the brain that also involves in language processing.

The International Dyslexia Association has defined dyslexia as follows: “a specific learning disability that is neurological in origin. It is characterized by difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition and by poor spelling and decoding abilities. These difficulties typically result from a deficit in the phonological component of language that is often unexpected in relations to other cognitive abilities and the provision of effective classroom instruction. Secondary consequences may include problems in reading comprehension and reduced reading experience that can impede the growth of vocabulary and background knowledge” (Lyon, Shaywitz, & Shaywitz, 2003, p.2).

In analyzing the operating definition of dyslexia, the three core or primary symptoms (also known as the triad of inabilities) are (1) difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition, (2) poor spelling, and (3) poor decoding (also means poor basic reading skills). The underlying problem or what is termed as correlated symptom is the phonological processing deficit. As a result, the consequential or secondary symptoms of dyslexia are problems in reading comprehension and reduced reading experience. These symptoms, in turn, impede vocabulary development and growth of background knowledge.

Dysorthographia (EDM Level I LD, Level II LD 5.00)

Very little research to date has been done on children identified and/or diagnosed with spelling disability/disorder or dysorthographia. The term *dysorthographia* itself is not widely known or used in the literature of special education. Most of the time, such children severely poor in spelling are treated as dyslexic and are seldom or never grouped separately as dysorthographic to be intervened differently from others.

Dysorthographia (or spelling disability or disorder) is not yet an official term. The dysfunctional spelling has to do with orthography, which refers to correct or standard spelling in general (Richards, Platt, & Weber, 1985). When the prefix *dys* is added to the word *orthography*,

dysorthographia becomes a term referring to a specific learning disability associated with poor performance in spelling (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2006).

Currently, dysorthographia cannot be found listed in either the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-Fourth Edition-Text Revision (DSM-IV-TR) (American Psychiatric Association, 2000) or the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Health Related Problems-Tenth Revision-Second Edition (ICD-10R-2) (World Health Organization, 2004). However, the term can be found the Educator's Diagnostic Manual of Disabilities and Disorders (EDM) (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007) under the disability category of specific learning disabilities EDM Level I LD, Level II LD 5.00. The EDM has listed the following diagnostic symptoms of dysorthographia basing on the types of spelling errors committed: "addition of unneeded letters, omission of needed letters, reversals of vowels, reversals of syllables, phonemic spelling of non-phonemic words, and/or difficulty in understanding the correspondence between sounds and letters" (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007, p.31). However, errors alone cannot define clearly what dysorthographia is since such error types are also noted in children with dyslexia and dysgraphia in reading and writing respectively.

Chia (2009) has defined dysorthographia as "a developmental disorder (which means it is of constitutional origin) or it is an acquired disorder due to an external insult to the brain, characterized by a durable defect of assimilation of morphological and/or phonological rules resulting in the deterioration of the spontaneous written expression or under dictation" (p.120). Bosse (2008) has identified dysorthographia as the inability to remember lexical spelling caused by serious deficit in phonological processing. However, this phonological processing deficit cannot fully explain why there are children, who are able to read words using an analytic procedure, but still unable to memorize their spelling.

Studies (see Sterling & Robson, 1992, for detail) on children with dysorthographia have identified the following problems they encounter such as, slowness and poverty of written expression with lots of hesitations (Tay, 2005); committing linguistic errors relating to grammar, conjugation and spelling (Funnell, 1992); writing difficulties similar to those relating to dyslexia (see Bosse, 2008; Nicolson, Pickering, & Fawcett, 1992); errors in copying with arbitrary misspellings (Funnell, 1992; Sterling & Seed, 1992); and spelling errors due to additions, omissions, substitutions and reversals of letters and/or syllables (Chia, 1996). According to Pierangelo and Giuliani (2007), "[S]pelling problems, like reading problems, originate with language learning weaknesses. Spelling does not reflect a general visual memory problem but a more specific problem with awareness of and memory for language structure including the letters in words (International Dyslexia Association, 2005)" (p.31).

In short, the triad of inabilities in dysorthographia consists of three core symptoms: (1) poor spelling, (2) poor copying (distal or proximal) and (3) slow and deprived written expression. The underlying symptoms are deficits in linguistic processing that involves poor integration of morphological, phonological and syntactic components of language caused by poor awareness and memory of language structure.

Visual Processing Disorders (EDM Level I L, Level II LD 12.00)

Visual processing disorder is a perceptual processing disorder that hinders the ability to process information through the eyes. It can cause lifelong challenges with everyday activities (e.g., copying words or numbers, spelling, remembering telephone numbers, reading a map or street directory). Such problems include differentiating between two similar letters, objects or shapes, or noticing the similarities and differences between certain colors, patterns, sizes or shapes. The disorder can happen without any vision impairment. The condition has nothing to do with poor eye-sight or sharpness of vision. The difficulties lie in processing of visual information and how it is interpreted by the brain (National Center for Learning Disabilities, 2004).

For young children who display difficulty in staying focused during a lesson or an activity, the initial follow-up action is to check for visual immaturity. In primary schools, all children have to go through a vision screening administered at school health team when they are in the lower primary level. Poor vision can attribute to difficulty in processing visual information. For example, many children do encounter difficulties with eye teaming, which allows both eyes to work together to process information. When there are problems with eye teaming, extra strain will be placed on the eyes, making it harder for a child to read, write, or perform other visual tasks. Hence, a child experiencing eye teaming difficulties can pay attention on visual tasks for short periods and often complains of headache, blurred or double vision, difficulty to concentrate and closes or covers one eye while reading. However, such problems should not be mistaken for visual processing disorder.

According to Spivey (2012), the key areas that the visual processing disorder can affect are (1) visual discrimination, which involves comparing and contrasting features of different colors, letters, objects, patterns and/or shapes; (2) visual figure-ground, which involves distinguishing images (e.g., shapes or letters/characters) from their background, as in seeking specific information on a printed page, and/or being able to recognize images within a competing background; (3) visual sequencing, which involves arranging objects in a particular order or distinguishing an order of images, symbols or words (e.g., having difficulties in staying in the right place when reading, and reversing letters in words or individual digits in bigger numbers); (4) visuo-motor processing, which uses feedback from the eyes to coordinate movement of other parts of the body, (e.g., copying from the whiteboard at a distance or from a book placed right in front); (5) visual memory, which involves recalling something seen recently or not too long ago; (6) visual closure, i.e., knowing what something is when only parts of it are shown or when certain features are omitted or missing; and (7) visual-spatial awareness, i.e., understanding the position of an object in space in relation to oneself (e.g., being near or far).

In short, the triad of inabilities in visual processing disorder consists of difficulties in (1) perceptuo-motor sequential processing by sight, (2) interpreting of visuo-spatial information in terms of features, figure-ground differentiation and/or closure, and (3) visual memory storage and retrieval.

HOW DO THEY DIFFER FROM EACH OTHER?

In summing up the para-symptomatological profiles of the three specific learning disabilities (see Table 1 on the next page), there are obvious differences among them in terms of the triad of core symptoms (or inabilities).

Interestingly, dyslexia and dysorthographia share a common core symptom, that is, poor spelling. Although poor spelling can be the result of phonological processing deficit, it fails to explain why, unlike children with dyslexia, there are those children with dysorthographia, who can read words using an analytic procedure, but are still unable to spell or memorize their spelling. Poor spelling can also be the result of deficits in visual processing, especially in perceptuo-motor sequential processing by sight (especially if a child is still at logographic phase of spelling development) or poor visual memory storage and/or retrieval, but no problems noted in auditory processing of words in reading and/or spelling.

Table 1. Para-symptomatological differences among the three specific learning disabilities

Triad of Core Symptoms	Reading Disorder (Dyslexia)	Spelling Disorder (Dysorthographia)	Visual Processing Disorder
First symptom	Difficulties with accurate and/or fluent word recognition	Poor spelling	Difficulties in perceptuo-motor sequential processing by sight
Second symptom	Poor spelling	Poor copying (distal or proximal)	Difficulties in interpreting of visuo-spatial information in terms of features, figure-ground differentiation and/or closure
Third symptom	Poor decoding (also means poor basic reading skills)	Slow and deprived written expression	Difficulties in visual memory storage and retrieval

It is possible for children with dyslexia who manifest visual processing difficulties and they are more likely those with dyseidetic dyslexia (EDM Level I LD, Level II LD 4.00, Level III LD 4.04) which is also known by other names such as visual dyslexia, dyseidesia or surface dyslexia. This is a Level III LD 4.04 for Level II LD 4.00 dyslexia and must not be confused with Level II LD 2.00 visual processing disorder. In the proper protocol of assessment in diagnosing a child and deciding if he/she has the condition of Level III LD 4.04 or Level II LD 2.00, then the one which is at the deeper level (i.e., Level III) will take precedence over the one (i.e., Level II) above it. This is because one needs to satisfy more diagnostic symptomatological criteria for the specific type of the disorder at Level III than at Level II. In other words, on top of the standard psycho-educational assessment, e.g., Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (WISC) for the psychological testing and Wechsler Individual Achievement Test (WIAT) for educational achievement test, and the Dyslexia Screening Test for the confirmation of dyslexia, at Level II LD 4.00, an additional specialized assessment for a specific type of disorder (e.g., Jordan Dyslexia Screening Test to identify if the disorder is auditory dyslexia, visual dyslexia and/or dysgraphia) has to be administered to confirm the Level III LD 4.04 dyseideia so as to rule out other possibilities. For Level II LD 12.00, it is essential to administer the Developmental Test of Visual Perception to confirm the condition of visual processing disorder in addition to WISC and WIAT administration.

Table 2 shows the summary of the standard assessment protocol using WISC, WIAT and other specific specialized assessment/screening tools to confirm the different disabilities/disorders as stated in the EDM Level I, Level II and Level III. The commonly administered psychological test is the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children but there are also many other IQ tests (e.g., Slosson Full-Range Intelligence Test). The commonly administered individual educational/achievement test is the Wechsler Individual Achievement Test but again there are also many other such tests

(e.g., Peabody Individual Achievement Test). As for the specific disability assessment or screening tools, there is a wide repertoire of them, e.g., Dyslexia Screening Test and Gilliam Autism Rating Scale. More specific disability screening tools include Gilliam Asperger Disorder Rating and ADHD Rating Scale, to list two examples here.

Table 2. Psycho-educational assessments and other additional specialized assessments

EDM Levels	Triad of Core Symptoms	Reading Disorder (Dyslexia)	Spelling Disorder (Dysorthographia)	Visual Processing Disorder
Level I	Examples of psychological testing	Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children	Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children	Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children
Level I	Examples of educational/ achievement testing	Wechsler Individual Achievement Test	Wechsler Individual Achievement Test	Wechsler Individual Achievement Test
Level II	Examples of disability screening	Dyslexia Screening Test	Dyslexia Screening Test	Developmental Test of Visual Perception
Level III	Examples of specific disability screening	Jordan Dyslexia Screening Test	<i>Phophilo</i> Screening Test (only for French)	McMaster Handwriting Assessment Protocol
Level IV	Very specialized testing or screening tools that are administered to target at the specific subtypes of the specific disorder			
Level V	Basing on the results obtained from the administration of the psychological and educational or achievement testing as well as disability and/or specific disability (and if needed to, a specific subtype of the specific disability) screening to determine the degree of adverse effect in terms of learning and/or behavioral needs in order to make a clear decision on which tier of intervention to be administered.			

CONCLUSION

The EDM has provided a good guide or protocol for classifying different specific learning disabilities at Level II once we have identified which category that a disability or disorder should fall under in the IDEIA classification of the thirteen disabilities at Level I. In this way, it allows us to move into the next Level III which specific type of the disorder we are looking at. In this paper, we have not gone own to Level IV which concerns the specific subtype of the specific type of the disorder. The last and final phase in the EDM multilevel coding system is Level V which concerns the degree to which the disability adversely affects the individual’s educational performance.

However, for practical reasons, the educational/achievement testing in this final Level V has been shifted to merge with Level I assessment in order to be placed at the same level as the psychological testing for the purpose of profiling an individual suspected to have some form of disability so that a treatment plan can be devised for the client. Deviating away from the EDM Level V, I suggest that it should be replaced with decision making on which level of intervention (Tier 1, 2 or 3) according to the Response to Intervention (RtI) Initiative (RTI Action Network, n.d.) depending on the degree of severity, which can only be determined by the full psycho-educational assessment.

Briefly, according to the RTI Action Network (n.d.), the Tier 1 intervention is for those who need to have high-quality, scientifically based instruction, differentiated to meet their learning and behavioral needs. These individuals will be screened periodically in order to identify those who

continue to struggle and need further or additional support. Next, the Tier 2 intervention is for those who are not making progress in meeting the goals set in the mainstream curriculum and they need increasingly intensive instruction to cater to their learning and behavioral needs according to their individual levels of performance and rates of progress. Finally, the Tier 3 intervention is for those who need customized intensive interventions to target at their skill deficits to remedy existing problems and to prevent more severe problems in future.

References

- American Psychiatric Association (2000). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders-fourth edition-text revision (DSM-IV-TR)*. Washington, DC: The Author.
- Bosse, M.L. (2008). *Dysorthographia*. Retrieved [on-line] on November 14, 2008: <http://w3.pdps.univtlse2.fr/pagepersoBosseEnglish.html>.
- Broca, P. (1861). Perrte de la parole. Ramollissement chronique et destruction partielle du lobe anterior gauche du cerveau. *Bulletin et Memoires de la Societe d' Anthropologie de Paris*, 2, 219.
- Chia, N.K.H. (1996). *Teaching spelling to Singaporean primary three Chinese children who are poor spellers of English words*. Unpublished dissertation of the master of education (M.Ed) degree in language and literacy, Edith Cowan University, Perth, Western Australia.
- Chia, N.K.H. (2009, Spring). Teaching spelling to Singaporean Chinese children with dysorthographia in English language: Lexical versus lexical-phonological approach. *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*, 120-159.
- Elliott, J.G, and Grigorenko, E.L. (2014). *The dyslexia debate: Cambridge studies in cognitive and perceptual development*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Funnell, E. (1992). On recognizing misspelled words. In C.M. Sterling and C. Robson (Eds.), *Psychology, spelling and education* (pp.87-99). Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters.
- International Dyslexia Association (2005). Common signs of dyslexia. Retrieved [online] from: http://www.interdys.org/servlet/compose?section_id=5&page_id=49.
- Lyon, G.R., Shaywitz, S.E., and Shaywitz, B.A. (2003). A definition of dyslexia. *Annals of Dyslexia*, 53, 1-14.
- National Center for Learning Disabilities (2004). *Auditory processing disorders: In detail*. Retrieved [online] from: <http://www.nclld.org/index.php?option=content&task=view&id=473>.
- Nicolson, R.I., Pickering, S., and Fawcett, A.J. (1992). Spelling remediation for dyslexic children using the self-spell programs. In C.M. Sterling and C. Robson (Eds.), *Psychology, spelling and education* (pp.250-267). Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters.
- Pierangelo, R., and Giuliani, G. (2006). *Learning disabilities: A practical approach to foundations, assessment, diagnosis, and teaching*. Boston, MA: Pearson Education.
- Pierangelo, R., and Giuliani, G. (2007). *The educator's diagnostic manual of disabilities and disorders (EDM)*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Richards, J., Platt, J., and Weber, H. (1985). *Longman dictionary of applied linguistics*. Essex, UK: Longman Group.
- RTI Action Network (n.d.) *Tier instruction/intervention*. Retrieved [online] from: <http://www.rtinetwork.org/essential/tieredinstruction>
- Shaywitz, B. (1995). Sex differences in the functional organization of the brain for language. *Nature*, 373, 607-609.
- Shaywitz, S. (1996, November). Dyslexia. *Scientific America*, 98-105.

- Spivey, B.L. (2012). Visual processing disorder: How does this affect learning. *Handy Handouts*, No. 372. Retrieved [online] from: www.handyhandouts.com.
- Sterling, C.M., and Robson, C. (Eds.). *Psychology, spelling and education*. Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters.
- Tay, S.K.H. (2005). *Understanding childhood learning disorders: Clues to their diagnosis and management*. Retrieved [on-line] on November 10, 2008: http://www.med.nus.edu.sg/paed/academic/NEU_understanding_childhood_learning.htm
- US Department of Education (2004). *Twenty-sixth annual report to Congress on the implementation of IDEA*. Washington, DC: US Department of Education.
- World Health Organization (2004). *International statistical classification of diseases and related health problems-tenth revision-second edition (ICD-10-2)*. Geneva, Switzerland: The Author.